

New Innovative Policies and Strategies for Retail Success

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Abstract

The Indian retail industry has been thrown open to foreign majors and is packed with players who strive to offer great products and value-for-money to Indian consumers. The country holds a vast promise for retailers with its burgeoning spending power and a rising middle class. The US\$ 500 billion Indian retail markets, growing at an annual rate of about 20 percent, is largely dominated by small shops and 'kirana' stores as of now. The organized retail segment is in its nascent stage and has a huge potential to harness in the sub-continent. Foreign giants like Wal-Mart and IKEA have recently received the Government's nod to enter into the Indian market, after making all the necessary compliances. This paper provides the tactics followed by the retail sector.

Keywords: Retail Industry and Organized retail segments

Introduction

The retail sector is expanding and modernizing rapidly in line with India's economic growth. It offers significant employment opportunities in all urban areas. The India Retail Industry is the largest among all the industries, accounting for over 10 percent of the country's GDP and around 8 percent of the employment. The Retail Industry in India has come forth as one of the most dynamic and fast paced industries with several players entering the market. The India Retail Industry is gradually inching its way towards becoming the next boom industry. Indian retail is dominated by a large number of small retailers consisting of local Kirana shops; owner manned general stores, chemists, footwear shops, paan, beedi shops, hawkers, etc. which together make up the 'unorganized retail' or traditional retail. The last three or four years have witnessed the entry of some organized retailers opening stores in various modern formats in metros and other important cities.

The growth of organized retailing in recent years can also be gauged by the rise of shopping malls as well as the rising number of modern retail formats. In 1999 India had only three shopping malls measuring less than one million square feet. Shopping in India has witnessed a revolution with the change in consumer buying behavior

and the format of shopping. The retail industry in India has modernized, and this can be seen from the fact that there are multi-stored malls, huge shopping centers, and sprawling complexes, which offer food, shopping & entertainment all under the same roof. The market witnessed a shift in trend from traditional retailing to organized retailing. The purchasing power of Indian urban consumer is growing and branded merchandise in categories like apparels, cosmetics, shoes, watches, beverages, food, and even jewelry, is slowly becoming lifestyle products that are widely accepted by the urban Indian consumer. Indian retailers need to take the advantage of this growth and to aim to grow, diversify and introduce new formats to pay more attention to the brand building process.

The Secret of Retail Business Success

The following are the success tactics followed by the retailer in different sectors of the retail industry.

Decoy Pricing

This tactic is used by many stores. If a product worth Rs 1,000 is placed next to those worth Rs 500 and Rs 1,100, we are likely to pick the Rs 1,000 product and think of it as a good deal. It's a diversion to make the costly items seem economical. It's also used in restaurants, where menus list high-cost items next to cheaper ones.

Open the Wallet

At the checkout counter, there will be small items like low-priced wallets, accessories, snacks and chocolates. They are there for a reason. After an exhaustive shopping session, we are easy prey with little self-control. So we will easily succumb to chocolates and small items.

Gruen Transfer

If we feel lost in big stores, it's intentional. Named after mall architect Victor Gruen, the term refers to building designs that confuse shoppers and make them spend more time so that they make impulse buys. Crossing the same spot again also makes us less price-sensitive due to the false feeling of price familiarity.

Bag Snare

If we wondered why we are instantly handed a carry bag in a clothes chain or a supermarket? One, if we have to hold stuff in our hand, we are likely to buy fewer things. Two, they play on our loss aversion bias, which means that the longer we have the thing in our possession, the more the sense of loss while parting with it. So ditch that bag.

Denomination Effect

This cognitive bias is exploited freely by shops. It makes a person less willing to use a higher denomination note than a lower one. So while we are unlikely to buy a big shampoo bottle worth Rs 400, we won't mind spending Rs 100 on a smaller one. The shops display more such items. This is also why we buy a Rs 10 candy at the cash counter.

Dynamic Pricing

Most online retailers use this trick, offering different prices to different customers as per demand. This means that if we have been on a website for long, we may be offered a higher price as opposed to one who has stayed for a very short period. This is because the user's browsing and spending patterns can be tracked by online retailers. To avoid it, browse incognito, erase cookies and log out of our account.

Eyelevel Products

It may not have struck us, but the products that are at eye level are typically costlier and more profitable than the ones on the bottom rack or higher up. Similarly, toys, games and other stuff for children will be placed at the lower level as per the kids' ages and heights. The stores also tend to move customers from right to left because most people are right-handed and find it easier to grab stuff as they go past aisles.

Essential Items at the End

Essential food items are typically placed at the end of a grocery store or supermarket so that we are forced to cross the aisles loaded with other, attractive stuff. So, even if we had no intention of picking the items and these were not present in our shopping list, we will be tempted to buy, and most often do.

Discount Traps

'Buy one, get second at 50%' or 'Buy one, get one free' don't make for good offers. The first one is only providing a 25% discount on each item. In the latter, the price may cover both items. Online sales may also offer discounts with limited validity or on the next purchase.

Small Packages Sell Big

If we think we are saving money by buying items that come in packs, say, a six-pack of juice cartons or probiotic packs, think again. Research shows that we invariably end up consuming more over time, a smart way to make us spend more each time. So unless we are entertaining or planning a trip, try not to go in for the 'economical' packs.

Free Samples

The free sample stations strategically placed in malls and grocery stores are not just a marketing strategy for a new product or eatable but are also intended to make us linger around and buy other items placed in the area or aisles positioned next to these stations.

Mesh Bags Costlier

The vegetables packed in mesh bags were for our ease of picking and carrying? Not always. They are costlier than loose items, and may also be a mix of good and damaged items. So it may be more cost-effective to spend five more minutes and pick the vegetables by hand.

Downloading Apps

If we downloaded e-commerce apps on our phone, Even if we are not an avid shopper, we may succumb to regular alerts and messages of early-bird notices and buy things just because they are on sale or make impulse purchases for items that we don't need.

Forced Urgency

If we tried to book a hotel via an aggregator, we are likely to have come across pop-ups that tells us '11 people are checking this hotel' or 'Only two rooms left on this site.' Similarly, many online and offline sales flash 'Last few days' or 'Only five items left' signs to force us to take action and loosen our purse strings.

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